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The Manager's Competence of Socio-Cultural Activity in Measuring Socio-Cultural Effects

Abstract: *Introduction.* Transformational processes in Ukraine lead to increased public demand for the spread of innovative technologies of social and cultural activity. The measuring of the effects of social and cultural activity is a necessary element of many social and cultural technologies. Formation of the competence to measure social and cultural effects of managers of social and cultural activities requires careful theoretical, methodological and methodical substantiation. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is to substantiate the theoretical and methodological components of the educational technology of formation the competence to measure of social and cultural effects in system of abilities of future managers of social and cultural activity. In the course of the research a set of fundamental ideas of the activity approach, general systems theory, structural analysis, social, economic and psychological determinism, as well as methods of pedagogical observation, student testing, interviewing and interrogatory, text analysis of student projects were applied. *Results.* The expediency of profound formation of competence to measure of social and cultural effects in the professional training of managers of social and cultural activity is revealed. The content of social and cultural influence that makes a shift in the life activity of the individual and the society is shown. The concept of social and cultural effects, which exists as a scientific term and is accessible for scientific measurement, has been clarified. *Conclusions and discussion.* The scientific novelty of the obtained results is the confirmed

expediency of pre-emptive mastery of theoretical approaches to measuring social and cultural effects and supplementing the theory of social and cultural activity with new theoretical definitions of the concepts of “social and cultural influence”, “social and cultural effect” and “measurement of social and cultural effects”. The practical significance of the obtained results is reflected in their direct use in the process of training of managers of social and cultural activities.

Keywords: professional training of managers of socio-cultural activity, socio-cultural influences, socio-cultural effects, measurement of socio-cultural effects, the competence to measure of socio-cultural effects.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. Training of higher education specialists in the specialty 028 “Management of social and cultural activity” in Ukraine has begun relatively recently. There are not many practical directions of social and cultural activity in which professional training of managers with bachelor's and master's degrees takes place. Those practical areas of social and cultural activity, which have already taken shape in Ukrainian society and have some legislative and very rarely financial support from the state, correspond to the level of development of the sphere of material production in Ukraine. The inhibition of the potential for rapid development of macro- and microeconomics over 28 years is not deliberate and arbitrarily organized. But no unplanned factors of manifestation of lack of expediency, spontaneity, unmanageability “work” not only in the fields of economy and politics. It is likely that the domestic branches of social and cultural activity are experiencing the greatest lag behind its European models.

Applicants for bachelor's and master's degrees in social and cultural management are studying in many Ukrainian higher education institutions. The courses of study at universities in different regions are almost completely repeated. Therefore, the problem today is finding new directions that would meet the needs of modern Ukrainian society and the tasks of economic and cultural European integration, reflecting the tendencies of renewal of socio-political and socio-economic reality. In addition, innovative social and cultural technologies of the modern type are able to serve as renewal tools in various spheres of political-administrative, legal, educational and civic life of society.

Objectively, there is a growing public demand for the distribution of new practical directions of social and cultural activity for Ukraine, the transformation of certain types of social and cultural activity into the sphere of business. In recent years, an avalanche of social and cultural projects with signs of innovation has emerged. Therefore, there is a growing need for rapid development of methodological approaches and theoretical generalizations

of the phenomenon of social and cultural activity in general, and in related fields of knowledge also. Numerous organizational, methodological and didactic issues of higher professional education of specialists in the management of social and cultural activity are still pending. Problems of modern methodological approaches to teaching students in the specialty “Management of social and cultural activities”, have not yet received widespread discussion in professional publications. Including the methodological conditions for the formation of competence to measure of social and cultural effects in student-seekers degree “Bachelor of management of social and cultural activity” has not been discussed yet.

State study of the problem. Efforts to find out the essence of social and cultural influences, to understand the mechanisms of their actualization in the socialization and enculturation of the individual, the enculturation and humanization of society, to master the techniques and technologies of conscious control over them observe throughout the development of civilization in various theories and videos. Numerous conceptual approaches have historically been implemented in variable political-managerial, economic, legal, social-pedagogical, religious, esoteric, social-ecological, artistic, leisure, valeology and cultural practices. De facto, the problem of the essence of social and cultural influence is the main issue of a wide range of sciences of philosophical, cultural, anthropological, sociological, legal, political, religious and artistic directions.

One of the channels of insight into the essence of social and cultural influences is to research them as cognitive activity and to search for its sources. The first theorists, which tried to understand social and cultural effects as steps of the individual from unreasonable, animal existence to purposeful and conscious imitation of objective laws of nature development, logic of the Logos, physical and physiological connections of things and their eidos, attracting influence of universal Ideas or Forms was Thales (1989), Heraclitus (1989), Democritus (Lurie, 1970), Plato (1968), Aristotle (1975). It is their concept that is the origin of the understanding of the connections between the objective logic of things and ideas, the logic of language and the subjective logic of thinking as social and cultural effects, which are indicators of the level of enculturation of society and its humanization. In such concepts, where emphasis is placed on epistemology, the rationality of the human worldview is perceived by the individual as a free subject – a member of the society, who has the responsibilities of rational social and cultural activity.

Doubts about the absolutization of rationality as a free choice and duty of each individual and an alternative to the epistemological approach to interpreting the meaning of culture have repeatedly been formulated in the ethics of the Stoics, Epicureanism, the doctrine of “psychological apperception” by G. Leibniz (2013), the concept of transcendental apperception by I. Kant (1964).

The interpretation of the history of the formation of new knowledge and skills and their inheritance in separate economic and political communities as creative social and cultural events, the elucidation of the objective propagation of legal and moral ideas, the formation of nations and political institutions as indicators of social and cultural activity where realized by Sh. L. Montesquieu (1955).

Continues to elucidate the historical achievements of mankind as indicators of the universal influence of social and cultural activity, these include political, economic, legal, artistic, religious communications, writing, languages, means of poetic and intellectual creativity, moral virtues, ethnic characters, forms of political organization J.-B. Vico (1940). The the universality concept of social and cultural influences on the development of European peoples and nations is concentrated in the conceptualization of the category of civilization by F. Gizo (1860). According to him, civilization is not a synonym for the concept of culture (enculturation), as it is sometimes considered, but an indicator of the success of social and cultural activity. This category is an indicator of the quality of the result of the development of humanity and personality. Therefore, it is a productive concept, the potential of which in modern cultural, social, humanitarian sciences is far from being exhausted.

The preoccupation with the hyper-optimistic expectations of planetary civilization effects of social and cultural activity waned in the nineteenth century. An open appeal to the idea of studying the local-geographical ethnic character occurs in the work of R. Owen (1881). The efforts to reflect national and ethnic incarnations of universal social and cultural development are united by the works of M. Kostomarov (2014), M. Drahomanov (1991), and M. Hrushevsky (2010). The search for ethnic indicators in common human civilization influences and common human traits in national and ethnic cultural achievements is the unifying slogan of Ukrainian cultural thought. Following this tradition, universal cultural and anthropological indicators of the effects of social and cultural activity have been identified as the main phylogenetic and ontogenetic degrees of humanization – hominization, sapientification and personification – in S. Krymsky's philosophical reflections (1996).

Ya. Martynyshyn and O. Khlystun (2018) substantiate the view that the reflection of the real or potential content of the influences of social and cultural activity is traditionally stored in the semantic field of the category “idea”. At the same time, at the fractures of social and cultural development, during periods of bifurcation renewal, the need for constructive ideas of political-ideological, political-managerial, political-economic, socio-political, moral-political, social-pedagogical content (p. 7-8) is exacerbated. The assertion that in the current conditions of the global planetary crisis and numerous risks

it is advisable to update the philosophical, methodological and epistemological category of “idea” is quite correct. The universal philosophical and methodological category “idea” is reflected in the concepts “management idea”, “political idea”, “moral idea”, etc. These concepts and corresponding lexical formations are transformed into the components of thinking and modern professional lexicon of relevant groups of specialists in social and cultural management. Each level of language functioning has its own creator and actor. These professional groups are able to find out new goals, perspectives, algorithms for further development and improvement of planetary life, which are concentrated in the variety of social and cultural meanings of the category “idea”.

In recent decades, the definition of cognitive and socio-psychological mechanisms of social and cultural influences, the search for theoretical approaches to assess their effects in Western science, marked by the emergence of a number of publications by R. Brodie (2004), F. Heylighen (1992a; 1992b), R. Dawkins (1993), D. Rushkoff (2010). The works of these theorists are united by the problems of studying the communicative mechanisms of formation, development, preservation and imitation of such social and cultural phenomena as politics, religion, art, science, etc.

An important achievement of these theories is the emphasis on the problem of human creativity as a major source of social and cultural innovation in society. The methodological approaches and terminology of philosophy, theories of communication, psychology, sociology, neurophysiology and genetics are widely used. The product of collective creativity was the formation of a synthetic approach called “Metasystem Transition Theory”, which in the media is often referred to as “memetics” in accordance with the term “meme” introduced by R. Dawkins. A biologist by profession, Dawkins formed a neologism “meme” by analogy with the term “gene” and used it as a well-understood model to popularize his reflections on the problem of social and cultural imitation of language, thinking, and models of consciousness, political and legal technologies of public administration, religious ideology, philosophical ideas and more. The concept of meme quickly became known, it was adopted as an effective tool for the theoretical study of social and cultural phenomena by experts in various fields of science. The definition of this term has appeared in many publications in the field of evolutionary biology, psychology and sociology. In addition to the concept of meme, in the following R. Dawkins also used the term “virus”. Therefore, some inattentive commentators have described in the media the content of theoretical studies of proponents of memetics as a reduction of cultural development to biological evolution. In addition, R. Dawkins also used the category “God” to explain the driving forces of cultural evolution, which in his memetic reflections is nothing more than a metaphor for the universal natural and social

and cultural tendencies of self-organization and self-improvement. R. Dawkins believed that comparing mechanisms of social and cultural progress with God would help ordinary readers better understand their causes. In fact, the mass media accused the memetics of mysticism.

However, for example, a theoretical account of the problem of characterization of the essence of culture and its transmission, contained in the Stanford Encyclopaedia, after J. Prinz, written entirely with the use of memetic terminology: “Memes”, “Cultural Epidemiology” (Prinz, 2011).

Unresolved issues. There is a contradiction between theoretical training and readiness for scientific research in the preparation of managers of social and cultural activity. Diagnostic and formative components of practical social and cultural technologies also typically include measurement tools. Competence to measure of the effect of social and cultural activity is formed in the search for bachelor's and master's degrees mainly in the direct process of developing a diploma research toolkit. This is where the greatest difficulties are experienced, in most cases students are not able to do this, which results in the choice of copying other anther's tools or simplifying research tasks before polling. Therefore, in our opinion, the problem of forming competence to measure of social and cultural effects in the bachelor's degree seeking higher education in the specialty “Management of social and cultural activity” deserves separate discussion in terms of its methodological, methodical and didactic aspects. Diploma and course studies are a necessary component of the preparation of bachelors and masters in the specialty “Management of social and cultural activities”. Overcoming the tendency to abstract existing publications, mainly textbooks and articles, distributed in the student environment, requires their training in research. The step-by-step complication of training programs involves moving from simple forms of research to becoming more qualified. However, all forms of organization of research activities in social and cultural fields require the formation of competence to measure social and cultural effects, the ability to develop tools that are suitable for the study of the effectiveness of social and cultural influences in its diagnostic, experimental, verification stages. According to the syllabus of Sumy State University (Ukraine) in the specialty “Management of social and cultural activities”, already in the second year course-oriented practical studies begin. Therefore, it is advisable to formulate a basic system of theoretical ideas and skills in the development of measurement procedures at the same time as learning the basics of social and cultural activity theory and cultural theory. From the point of view of the traditional sequence of content of theoretical disciplines and sociology and applied research techniques, this approach is proactive, aimed at the earliest possible formation of the leading professional competence of the manager of social and cultural activity.

Therefore, the main unresolved issue is the disclosure of substantive characteristics of competence to measure of social and cultural effects. At the same time, specifics of methodological conditions of mastering students of the specialty “Management of social and cultural activity” with this type of competencies should be determinate.

2. Purpose and research methods

The purpose of the article. The article reflects some results from the study of the process of formation of competence for measuring social and cultural effects in future specialists in the management of social and cultural activity. The general purpose of the research is the theoretical substantiation and experimental verification of the components of mastery of students of the specialty “Management of social and cultural activity” competence to measure of social and cultural effects. Thus, the generalization of the experience of three years of practical educational and methodological work with future managers of social and cultural activity is positioned and the level of solving the following tasks is available:

- determination of theoretical and methodological and methodological bases of formation of competence of the future manager of social and cultural activity on measurement of social and cultural effects as an initial condition of productive mastering by methods of research activity;
- statement of universality of measurement processes in social and cultural activity;
- disclosure of the content of social and cultural influence and clarification of the concept of social and cultural effects;
- proving the essence of measuring social and cultural effects as an assessment of the magnitude of the impact of a social and cultural event on the individual and on society;
- finding out social and personal indicators of the impact of social and cultural events and methods of their reflection;
- clarification of the features of the use of indicators of influence of social and cultural event in the development of measuring tools of social and cultural research.

The methodological basis of the study. The cognitive-communicative basis of the research is the conceptual paradigm of the activity approach to the study of anthrop, social and cultural phenomena. The methodological basis for the development of concepts “social and cultural influences”, “social and cultural effects”, “measurement of social and cultural effects”, “competence to measure social and cultural effects” are:

- a set of fundamental ideas of the general theory of systems, classical philosophy and theoretical cultural studies on the social and cultural essence

of human activities, structural analysis of human activities; the concept of numerous modules of being of human activities;

– understanding the categories of social and cultural influence, the effects of social and cultural activity, the measurement of social and cultural effects requires the use of the idea of economic determinism, psychological determinism, pragmatic-phenomenological and socio-typological approaches;

– disclosing the conceptual and terminological content of the categories “social and cultural influence”, “social and cultural effect”, as lexemes of everyday and scientific-theoretical terminus, is made using the historical-linguistic approach, some elements of etymological and semantic analysis;

– pragmatic phenomena of social and cultural influences and social and cultural effects are covered by the ideas of structural analysis of the human world-view and the theory of communication and social and cultural regulation. Formal (algorithmic) components of social and cultural influences and effects are considered as acting social and cultural regulations; content components are revealed as existential, cognitive, axiological and praxeological concepts that determine the vital activity of the individual and the society;

– competent paradigm was used to teach students complex theoretical material to reveal the categories of social and cultural influence, the effects of social and cultural activity, the measurement of social and cultural effects. The reduction of the concepts of “influence”, “effect”, “method”, “idea”, “technology”, “algorithm”, “regulation” to the tokens “competence” (or “knowledge”, “ability”, “skills”) can be considered as a useful didactic simplification. Or it can be interpreted as translating scientific-theoretical methodological language to the level of practical professional language of managers. Contemporary, Western and domestic implementation of the category “competence” in numerous management fields is likely to confirm the true scientific status of a productive “competence” approach.

Research methods. In the process of research work was used a set of various methods of scientific learning. *Theoretical methods* are used – *analysis* of philosophical, cultural, psychological, pedagogical literature, legal sources, periodicals in order to determine the state of elaboration of the problem of forming the competence of the manager of social and cultural activity to measure of social and cultural effects; *method of theoretical generalization and synthesis* – to determine the basic definitions of the study, generalization of the research results, substantiation of a complex of scientific, methodological and organizational-technological means of working with students, formulation of conclusions. *Empirical methods* used – pedagogical *observation*, *testing* of students to evaluate their attitude to particular components of the educational process, *interviewing* and *discussing* to determine the level of formation of new competence, *analysis of documents* (texts of student projects), which reflected the process of mastering students with the competence to measure of social and cultural effects on different target groups.

Research information base. The main basis of the information base of the research were own observations, which were recorded in the process of development and elaboration of organizational-technological, scientific-methodical, scientific-theoretical issues. Practical testing of research hypotheses was carried out on the basis of training of bachelors in the specialty “Management of social and cultural activity” at Sumy State University (Sumy, Ukraine). A significant component of the information base of the research were also modern developments in the organization of educational and methodological work in higher education, international documents on determining the components of the competence approach, etc.

3. Research results

In accordance with the defined purpose and tasks of the research, a complex of scientific-theoretical, scientific-methodical, organizational-technological issues was elaborated.

3.1. Determination of methodological conditions for forming the competence of the future manager of social and cultural activity to measure of social and cultural effects

The peculiarity of the organization of the educational process in the specialty “Management of social and cultural activities” at the Department of Psychology, Political Science and Social and Cultural Technologies of Sumy State University (Sumy, Ukraine) is its structuring on the basis of the original principle of “dual education”. Qualitative organization of dual education requires a deep systematic integration of theoretical and practical training, with emphasis on the development of competences for the formation and implementation of practical social and cultural projects of modern type. The main methodological and theoretical approaches to substantiation, practical approval and permanent creative enrichment of the dual education system are the subject of publications by O. Davlikanova, O. Kupenko, and N. Svitaylo (2016), and I. Petrova (2019). Generalized methodological and theoretical problems of acquiring a system of professional competences by students studying in the specialty “Management of social and cultural activity” are reflected in the publications of M. Asainova (2007), I. Lysakova (2013), N. Kochubey (2017); Ya. Martynishin, O. Khlystun, Ye. Kovalenko, A. Hrushina and O. Tadlya (Martynyshyn et al., 2017); Ya. Martynyshyn and Ye. Kovalenko (2018), O. Shcherbina-Yakovleva (2019).

The results of the study of the problem of competence formation to measure of social and cultural effects completely reflect the experience of the authors, accumulated during the training sessions from the theoretical section of the discipline “History and theory of social and cultural activity”. This discipline at Sumy State University (Sumy, Ukraine) is taught to students of the first year of the specialty “Management of social and cultural activities”.

The initial organizational requirement for the implementation of the principle of dual education in the educational process necessitates the complete rejection of abstract acquaintance of students with the theory of social and cultural activity within its cultural or philosophical paradigm. The variant of development of the theory of social and cultural activity, which is taught to students of the specialty “Management of social and cultural activity” – is practically oriented, that is, in fact, is the initial stage of preparation for the subsequent understanding of professional technologies. Practical orientation leads to consideration of each type of social and cultural activity in terms of two main issues: “how it works” and “what the goal it has”. At the same time, the university's requirement of the standard of professional education is to prepare students for the development of practical social and cultural projects. Consequently, these circumstances determine the main objectives of the discipline:

- to form into the students' consciousness a picture of social and cultural environment as a complex multilevel system, which is a product of human cultural activity;

- to bring to the students understanding of social and cultural activity as influential factor of changes, development, updating of life activity of society and personality;

- to approve professional clarification of the historical process of development of social and cultural activity as a stream of innovative attempts of various social and cultural technologies;

- to reveal the influence of social and cultural activity as its effectiveness;

- to explain the essence of measurement and measuring processes in technologies of social and cultural activity;

- to build initial cognitive foundations for students to develop competence to measure of social and cultural effects.

In the following semesters, the disciplines such as sociology, professional technology, the understanding of measurement procedures are expanded and developed. During the course and diploma studies, attempts to develop measuring instruments continue.

The basic principles of mastering professional knowledge and practical skills of a bachelor in the management of social and cultural activity are the formation of a complex of theoretical ideas about the essence of social and cultural activity, its specificity, forms of existence, mechanisms of development, etc. Students' mastery of knowledge about the historical diversity of social and cultural phenomena and their present-day abundance and multidimensionality has its difficulties. Overcoming simplistic stereotypes, that limit the understanding of the content of the social and cultural phenomena by expe-

rience of attending cafes and discos, as well as school educational activities or concert activities in a district cultural institution, is a conflict between the new knowledge, that the teacher has to prove, and the old, but personal acquired.

The most accessible to mastering students in the initial steps of vocational training is the idea of expressive phenomena of social and cultural activity as individual phenomena, interesting in terms of their technological features, historical and contemporary impact on the development of man, society, social institutions, etc. The phenomenological approach gives an opportunity to demonstrate the diversity of social and cultural activities that occur in societies of different geographical regions in successive historical epochs. The phenomenological approach qualitatively differs from the historical consideration by the wide use of comparisons, parallels, generalizations, retrospective and perspective reviews of social and cultural events, etc. This creates a cognitive basis for explaining the historical-genetic and ontological links of social and cultural life of society with nature, with emphasis on modern geopolitical, political-economic, socio-ecological, cultural-environmental, socio-pedagogical issues.

It is at the initial stage of the educational process that we try to overcome the initial contradiction of the mental development of freshmen. The unilateral notion that social and cultural activity is a sphere of leisure, entertainment, should be supplemented by knowledge of the diversity of its other types. Students are of the opinion that social and cultural phenomena in nature and content are also numerous forms of everyday, political, religious, legal, educational activities with some surprise. A standard feature of the intellectual development of graduates of the school of recent years, which we record in the educational process in the first year, is the formed opinion that social and cultural activity has nothing to do with the material aspect of society, economic and household activities. It is also stereotypical to identify the cultural and spiritual forms of activities.

Therefore, a lot of time is spent on clarifying questions about the essence of culture and its role in society, about the unity of material and spiritual in the fields of social and cultural activity. It is proved that the sphere of economic and household life in its social dimension is the basic subsystem of the existence of society in any historical era. Economic and household activity in society exists in two main dimensions: as socio-economic (organized within the whole society) and family household or individual household. In modern society, the sphere of economic and economic life has a complex structure. Its components include material production, banking and the provision of services related to the material life of society: trade, transport services, consumer services and more. Industry, agriculture are aimed at the production of material products that can meet the needs of society and each individual in the tools of labour, food, clothing, housing, household goods.

In today's society, the elementary, “basic” material needs are met under the conditions of intensive marketing, which is an important form of social and cultural activity. Rich media advertising, modern marketing projects with the use of electronic technologies and gadgets are a condition for the success of material production and trade. Effective development of material production is the basis for the dissemination of forms of social and cultural activity, such as organized tourism, sports, leisure and entertainment, hospitality and restaurant business, fashion and mass clothing industry, healthcare, museum, library and more.

An important sphere of human activity is household. It has a great influence on other spheres of social life, and above all – on work, social activity, mood and behaviour of people. The phenomenological dimension distinguishes between urban and peasant, family and individual life, life of different age groups, etc. The structure of household of different social groups can be considered in terms of the ratio of its material support and spiritual content, types of time spent (satisfaction of physiological needs, self-care, physical education and other types of valeological activities, domestic work, rest, leisure). Under the influence of social and geographical conditions in different peoples formed a complex of traditions, customs, rituals associated with everyday life. Different forms of life are formed in the city and the village. Thus, the sphere of life is a space for many types of individual and group social and cultural activities. There are deep prospects for developing projects to improve the quality of life, to shape contemporary needs and tastes, to influence the styles and lifestyles of different target groups.

Perceptions about the phenomenology of social and cultural activity are expanded when considering social and cultural problems of the existence of ethno-social and racial communities. Historical characteristics are complemented by an examination of the content and causes of conflict in contemporary racial-ethnic interactions. These issues are also related to the peculiarities of social and cultural activities of the church and religious denominations.

Gender differences of individuals and gender stratification of society in the historical and contemporary dimensions are embodied in numerous philosophical, cultural, religious ideological complexes, reflected in works of art, confirmed in the legislation. Gender phenomena are the cause of specific social and cultural and legal conflicts, an inexhaustible source of contradictory concepts and ideologies.

At present, attention is paid to the sphere of political life of society. Has the expression “political culture” been an outdated abstract in the last decades? We pay particular attention to the students that political relations in society, political consciousness, and political activity of each individual are the sphere of social and cultural activity that never loses its significance. Historical phenomenology of political activity has accumulated numerous

examples of realistic and utopian projects and models of managerial, social-transformational, communicative-regulatory directions. Today, projective social and cultural technologies of political content, focused on deepening the reflection of the basic needs of society and the individual in ordering public life, improving the functioning of state structures and legislation, are relevant. Innovative social and cultural technologies should aim at stabilizing the effects of the most acute contradictions of external and internal political activity, limiting the main risks of contemporary political activity of the population and self-expression of citizenship, counteracting the deprivation of some sections of the population in the sphere of civic activity. Social and cultural technologies of political content are able to reflect the substantive features of group and individual strategies of limiting political risks in the life of society, individual geographical regions, families, every citizen.

To deepen the theoretical knowledge, in our view, it is advisable to introduce students to the principles of a systematic view of the historical content of social and cultural activity. In the historical dimension in many forms of social and cultural activity there is continuity, repetition, copying. Therefore, in some cases it is advisable to use the term “social and cultural process”. This concept deepens the methodological understanding of the process of historical development of mankind, while it complements concepts such as “culture” or “cultural development”, “civilization”, revealing their inner meaning. Productive is also the implication of the concept of “social and cultural process” in studies of the life of individual societies – ethno-cultural, ethno-political, ethno-psychological, cross-cultural, etc.

We seek to assert in the minds of students the notion of the actual existence of a social and cultural process in at least two of its basic dimensions – objective and subjective.

In an objective dimension, the social and cultural process is a synergistic process of self-creation of the culture of society and their mutual enrichment. The social and cultural process in terms of the methodology of synergistic self-organization is spontaneous because it happens automatically, regardless of one's will and conscious intentions. The development of culture is the product and result of the development of the society, at the same time the society “consumes” culture as an artificial material and spiritual condition and the basis of daily life and development.

From a planetary point of view, the history of mankind occurs as a conditionally total process of the formation of society, the formation of culture, the formation of man in its renewed cultural and anthropological dimensions, and humanity as a combined subject of historical, cultural, civilization activity. This view also makes it impossible to consider the social and cultural process as reasonably organized. But paleo-anthropological, cultural-anthropological, and ethnological studies prove that already in the early sta-

ges of the prehistory and history of mankind in certain cultural regions, the most educated strata of the population realized subjective aspirations to maintain social stability by cultural means. These are aspirations of social self-government, appropriate organization of safety, management of certain processes of labour, educational activity, organization of social distribution of products of material production, counteraction to moral violations connected with thefts, control over sexual behaviour of teenagers, marriage and family relations and more. It is also an effort to form a group religious ideology as a tool for social governance and control.

As a scientific category, the notion of social and cultural process has productive methodological significance. The social and cultural process is incomplete, it is constantly ongoing. Looking towards the future, the social and cultural process is the object of such sciences as cultural studies, political science. Macroeconomics, reflecting the prospects for the development of means of meeting eco-cultural, ethno-cultural, scientific-cultural, educational needs, has related problems. In the popular leisure industries, microeconomic marketing research is rapidly developing.

The subjects of the deployment of social and cultural process in its global, objective dimension are humanity as a whole community, as well as individual ethnic groups, social groups, gender communities, religious, political, civic associations, asocial and antisocial groups, etc. The movement from pre-social, pre-cultural, pre-human to social and cultural life, embodied in specific types of human personality, is the objective content of the social and cultural process. In the phenomenological, objective-historical aspect, the social and cultural process is a productive component, the basis and active driving force of ethnic formation and state formation, the emergence and disappearance of professional social groups, religious trends and artistic, philosophical, scientific, esoteric, cultural subterranean commons, etc. Therefore, when studying individual historical and modern technologies of social and cultural activity, it is advisable to distinguish them from different levels of collective and individual subjects. The subjects of the social and cultural process in its objective-historical dimension are:

– collective actors at the macro-level, every next generation of adults trying to pass on their life experiences to the next generation of young people, using all existing social institutions (education, professional division of labour, arts, religion, etc.); the state and the church at those historical stages of development where they have already been built;

– collective subjects of the mess. These are ethnic communities at the stages of history that preserve their deep integration, post-integration ethno-cultural associations, professional schools and general educational institutions, political parties, ancient priestly secret communities, and modern religious denominations;

- collective subjects of micro-level – family, which is the main carrier of everyday traditions, customs, preservation of labour and family-pedagogical regulations, socio-psychological cultural-content stereotypes, etc.;
- individual subjects – creators, inventors of new forms and types of culture, creative, “charismatic” figures of politics, religion, art, philosophy, social and natural sciences, esoteric knowledge.

In the subjective sense, the social and cultural process is the accumulation of cultural and social competences by humanity. It occurs daily, step by step, like an uncontrollable and unconscious natural process. At every stage of the historical development of mankind in creative, innovative political, religious and other social and cultural theories, there has been and is a partial awareness and concentration of knowledge and ability to purposefully influence the person and society in significant situations, the concentration of means and tools of social and cultural influence, techniques, and methods. In the movie XX and beginning XXI century there are two main trends: the emergence of many empirical, pragmatically oriented social and cultural technologies that seek business, and the effort to develop generalized theoretical approaches to specific areas of social and cultural activity and social and cultural process as a global or regional-national phenomenon.

Introducing the category of social and cultural process in the study of the theoretical section of the discipline “History and theory of social and cultural activity” is appropriate in several aspects – in terms of the development of methodological competences of students and the extension of their linguistic apparatus. Understanding the meaning of “social and cultural process” by students helps to form in their minds initial methodological ideas about the development of culture as a whole.

3.2. Finding out the content of social and cultural influence and clarifying the concept of social and cultural effects

The outlined content of the initial theoretical training causes students to realize that the existence of a person within the social and cultural process as an object of his influence and active subject is an ontological fact, everyday being of man. Thus, psycho-emotional and cognitive conditions are created for the professional perception of the flow of social and cultural influences as the environment, and inner content of the existence of the individual.

The environment formed by the active flows of numerous social and cultural influences is conditionally systemic. This is the environment of society, so it is partially orderly. It is also largely chaotic. The contradictions of chaos and orderliness in the social and cultural environment of modern society are a separate theoretical and methodological issue and the sphere of innovative applied social and cultural technologies. It is advisable for first-year students to learn this look because they are aware of social and cultural influences as diverse in origin and content, as useful and useless, constructive

and destructive. Thus, social and cultural influences are perceived by students as the meaning of each person's life and self.

Social and cultural influences on personality, like any influential action, have their consequences. These consequences cover the areas of emotional response, sensory perception, cognitive development, intellectual attitude to the social and cultural environment, evaluative judgments and conclusions, the sphere of decision-making, the formation of individual goals and tasks, pragmatic actions, the formation of behavioural styles. They also need to be implemented as individual pragmatic social and cultural projects (in one's own life, gender, marriage and family sphere, branches of social creativity, business, etc.). This is how innovative models of social and cultural activity, diverse technologies that seek to change humanity, unite society with nature, overcome numerous contradictions, and so on, are born.

Cognitive immersion in the field of social and cultural phenomenology is very productive for the development of students' outlook, their general and professional awareness, and the impetus for imagination in creative projects in relevant fields. In general, at the end of the initial cycle of lectures and seminars, which discuss various aspects of social and cultural phenomenology and theory, previous disputes of the “school” level of professional thinking and harmful stereotypes can be considered overcome. At this stage of study, the complex of empirical ideas about the variety of types of social and cultural activity, and such theoretical concepts, as social and cultural activity, object of social and cultural activity, subject of social and cultural activity, types of social and cultural activity, technologies of social and cultural activity, the historical development of social and cultural activities, social and cultural process, etc.

3.3. Revealing the universality of measurement processes in social and cultural activity

The following set of lectures and practical classes is introduced on a sufficiently broad basis of the set of concepts from the theory of social and cultural activity and concepts of phenomenology, the general purpose of which is to prove the concept of the influence and effectiveness of social and cultural activity, the procedures for its evaluation and measurement. The practical tasks are to acquire knowledge and skills to develop simple types of tools for measuring the effectiveness of some components of available social and cultural technologies.

During the course of this cycle, the essence of assessment in social and cultural life is considered. The terms “estimate”, “price”, “value” are compared. Particular attention is paid to the concept of values. The problems of contradictions of the precious values of social and cultural objects and higher social and cultural values of personal and social existence are considered.

Measurement procedures are described in everyday life. The concepts of units of measurement, standards, and samples familiar to students are being activated. The role of empirical methods of measurement in the natural and exact sciences is emphasized, the relevance of the development of mathematical measuring approaches in socio-humanitarian and cultural studies are emphasized.

The effect category has been transferred to socio-humanitarian and cultural studies with technical knowledge, and literally means “action”, “change”, “shift”. In a broad sense, the effects are in general any consequence of the action of a certain (effective) factor. The consequences of action (effects) are measured in technical knowledge, predicted and projected using vector analysis and other mathematical methods. The idea of measuring social and cultural effects is confirmed by the implication of technical ways of developing units of measurement (impact indicators) and scales of various types as instruments of empirical research.

Mastering measurement procedures in social and cultural studies depends on understanding the effectiveness of social and cultural activity. At this stage of learning, the concept of social and cultural influence is compared with the concept of effects.

The basic theoretical concept underlying further educational work on the development of competence in the development of measurement tools is the concept of the effectiveness of social and cultural influence.

Problems of evaluating the effectiveness of anthropic systems (not technical, in which human activity is an active factor) are usually addressed by specialists in various fields of management. For example, the concept of effectiveness of managerial activity is revealed by *O. Shinkevich*. By his definition, “efficiency is the ratio of result (effect) and cost. An effect is a positive or negative result of an activity, reflected in conventional units, and received within a certain period from the realization of a certain activity” (2008, p. 141). In the field of social activity, this author highlights the main types of performance that affect the life of a particular subject (individual, group, organizational). The social sphere includes such an indicator as “the fact of achieving a social goal for more people or society in less time, with less staff and less expenditure” (2008, p. 141).

Productive in considering the problem of the effectiveness of social and cultural activity is drawing parallels and highlighting creative ideas in the field of social work theory.

The notions of efficiency and basic approaches to defining its criteria in the field of social work have been repeatedly discussed in publications by *V. Popov*. This author draws attention to the ambiguity of the notion of effectiveness when it is necessary to evaluate the results of social activity, which has an official institutional base in society. The definition of effectiveness in

this case has a scientific and practical sense. Science examines the effectiveness of providing social services to the population. From a practical and institutional point of view, efficiency is a system of guidelines for the activities of a social institute. In this case, the performance indicators reflect the demands and needs of different categories of the population, serve standards and standards of their satisfaction. In our opinion, the author emphasizes the specifics of quantitative and qualitative indicators (criteria) of effectiveness. The normative indicators and standards of work of the social institute are quite quantitative. Indicators that reflect the status of social service clients (individual, family, social group) are qualitative.

The author emphasizes that quantitative indicators are objective, available for calculation and measurement.

However, reflecting on the status of social service clients occurs through opinion polls. This process, she believes, is not a measurement at all (evidence-based scientific procedure). All the statements, judgments, and reasoning of the clients, in her opinion, are subjective, certainly wrong. According to this logic, such measures are proposed to limit the level of fallacy as increasing the number of respondents, as well as the predominant survey of experts, such as managers, specialists, employees of regulatory bodies, etc. (Popov, 1999, pp. 228-229).

K. Falkowskaia publications also discuss problems related to the interpretation of social work performance and the search for its criteria. It draws attention to the requirements of international organizations regarding the general goals and objectives of social work (the World Congress of Social Workers in Montreal), according to which the object of social work are barriers, inequality, injustice; it responds to crises and emergencies, as well as daily personal and social problems. Social work has a variety of skills, technologies and methods in its arsenal, working based on a holistic approach to the individual and their environment). Therefore, according to European requirements, the criteria for the effectiveness of this type of social activity are not external quantitative indicators, but internal, qualitative characteristics of human and social life.

K. Falkowskaia believes that this definition “does not have sufficient signs of instrumentality, that is, it is impossible to formulate the parameters of evaluating the effectiveness of social work. Social needs of different categories of the population, solving their social problems by management organizations, state and non-state social services, communities associations and non-profit organizations as well as representatives of active citizens means creating languages for their development” (2010, pp. 89-91). The author's assertion that the concept of “social work effectiveness” is abstract is quite correct, unless it is correlated with the real object, subject of activity or process of solving a social problem (technologies, methods, methods, etc.).

In the domestic development of problems of management of social and cultural activity is also discussed its effectiveness. For example, the overall approach of *N. Kochubey* is convincing, which bases its vision of performance criteria on European-style outlook. Therefore, an integrative understanding of the features of social and cultural activity requires consideration of the promotion of humanistic, human characteristics of social being, the orientation of the individual and social and cultural institutions to conscious purposeful cultural creation. According to the author, these characteristics are realized in the criteria of quality (spiritual content, activity of personality, balance of different types of social and cultural activity), criteria of effectiveness (achievement of a certain goal), criteria of subjective satisfaction (2017, pp. 33-34).

In this approach, we fully support the principle of cultural creation as the main qualitative feature of technologies of social and cultural activity, the content of its influence, the qualitative feature of its main effects.

However, we must deny that the term “effects of social and cultural activity” is merely its purpose. The effects are any influence whatsoever, change, and shift. Therefore, the terminological consideration of the original concepts of the theory of the effectiveness of social and cultural activity should continue.

Also, we do not fundamentally support the identification of terms “indicators”, “criteria” and “indicators”, their use as synonyms expressed by some authors. But this issue should also be the subject of special theoretical discussion beyond this article.

On the whole, the logic of theoretical consideration of these problems has already been sufficiently clarified, which gives grounds for introducing a constant set of conceptual concepts: the effects of social and cultural activity (result, influence, which is the object of scientific knowledge and measured by special instruments using conventional units of measurement), the effectiveness of social and cultural influence (systematic, integrative performance available to scientific measurement); social and cultural effects (large-scale effects, that can also be measured).

3.4. Proving the essence of measuring social and cultural effects as determining the magnitude of the impact of a social and cultural event on the individual and on society

Revealing the essence of social and cultural influence and its effectiveness helps to appeal to the fundamental ideas of classical philosophical methodology. The most profound and productive in solving this theoretical problem is the system-synergistic approach. One of the options for its implementation was expressed by *K. Popper*. A key concept that reveals the meaning of any social and cultural influence formulated by this philosopher as the basis of cultural-anthropological and social and cultural theory: a person has an “innate need to invent ordering.” *K. Popper* argues that “ordering” is a common feature of social and cultural activity, and occurs in all areas of

human thinking and practice, fields of science, technology, engineering, politics, etc. (1995, p. 118).

A person, like an artificial electronic device, is capable of forming new, more functionally optimal “structures in structures” – higher-level ordering – from previous information entities. This is precisely the function of social and cultural influences from an informational, systemic and structural point of view. Over the course of tens of millennia of the evolution of the neurophysiologic system, *Homo Sapiens* has developed its ability to accumulate significant amounts of information, as well as to synthesize, integrate new orderings, the basis of heuristic behaviour, creative inventions, and the like.

Some aspects of these processes are studied in psychological and pedagogical sciences, mainly in aspects of the psychology of creativity and school didactics. But holistic scientific development of this problem is yet to come.

The profound meaning of “ordering” is the accumulation of inherited social and cultural structures by each individual and the formation of their own, unique categorical-conceptual complex of means of understanding each individual thing and the environment as a whole, as well as algorithms for organizing practical actions. Logical and methodological problems and theoretical approaches to substantiate the structural view of social and cultural activity, productivity of allocation of categorical-conceptual subsystems in outlook-orienting and practical-regulatory entities in methodological, diagnostic, shaping technologies of social and cultural activities was learning by *O. Shcherbina-Yakovleva* (2017a; 2017b; 2019).

Selecting a separate category – categorizing the familiar environment – is associated with forming a subjective action program with that thing – the concept of action. The categories of things and their properties that people use as guidance in their activities answer the question “what is it, why is it”. Action concepts answer the question “what does this thing do?”.

Categories and concepts are the first, most straightforward level of human awareness of the world and a means of ensuring individual expediency. Formed categories are indicated by linguistic means. “In everything that appears to man by something internal, in general, in all that he does to his own, language has penetrated, and everything that he transforms into language and expresses in language, build or in annoyance, in a confused or more elaborate form, a certain category” (Hegel, 1970, p. 82).

The simplest categories that a person is guided by in everyday life are sensually-perceptual and logical (thinking) reflections of the form of things, their quantitative features, colours, textures, modes of movement, functions; dependence on the simple laws of nature and the like.

The process of “ordering” occurs mainly in unconscious forms. Conscious “ordering” is associated with creative activity. This process is primarily reflected in the verbal language. In other forms of social communication

in which a person manifests his personality, the desire for ordering is embodied in the invention of tools and technologies of work, in works of art, artistic word, and fantasy, religious and esoteric ideologies, of social and cultural utopias, rational-logical, philosophical, political-managerial, social-pedagogical projects.

The categories that an adult focuses on in everyday acts of practical life, as well as in concept, are, for the most part, unknowable, “invisible” to the average person. The exceptions to everyday life are those categories and concepts that we consider to be a reflection of the credo and usually have their verbal name.

But the search for the effects of social and cultural influences requires a deepening of their awareness and the development of research tools. The study of the effectiveness of social and cultural influences, among other methods, uses general-communicative analytical methods – thesaurus, linguistic-structural analysis, and such sociological method as content analysis. A variety of measurement tools can be developed using conceptual ideas and methods of social communication theory. The approach to the construction of measuring instruments using the concepts of general theory of social and cultural regulation, the main aspects of which is developed by A. *Shcherbina* (2013), is promising. In some efforts, one may read, see, or hear essential categories and behavioural concepts in one's own activity or in the behaviour of another person.

“... Humanity has transformed its controlled connections with the world into a means of expression. Language symbolizes have the triumph of human genius, outweighing even the advances of modern technology” (Whitehead, 1990, pp. 329-330). All kinds of social and cultural influences are involved in the formation of concepts of activity: conscious and unconscious, verbalized and non-verbalized, “managed” and “unmanaged”. Concepts (as well as concepts as a system of related subject concepts) exist in individual and social (group) models of action and problem solving. Therefore, they are available for fixation in social and cultural observation and for measuring by means of specially designed scales.

Social and cultural influences on the individual are predominantly in the form of an “environment-man” connection. In this case, the individual is the object of social and cultural influence. The subjects of social and cultural influences, as always, are multimodal: these are other people and I, family, recreational, micro-cultural and professional groups, social institutions, works of art. Objective factors, such as the socio-ecological environment, urban and rural landscapes, etc., also have influential functions. The totality of social and cultural influences in their systemic unity is equal to the influences of the factors by which anthropo-formation, socialization, and enculturation occur. In terms of the role of social and cultural influences in the development of society, it is still necessary to emphasize institutionalization, social reforms, social revolutions, etc.

3.5. Characteristics of social and personal indicators of the impact of social and cultural events and methods of their reflection

The content of concepts of individual worldview is formed by social and cultural environment, formed in personal life experiences. The means of influencing a person's social and cultural systems through various channels of social communication is to limit human behaviour and its transformation from spontaneous, impulsive natural forms into socially organized orderly and relatively intelligent ones. The result of integration at the level of individuality of a multilevel complex of influencing people is its sociality – transformation into a social individual, as well as enculturation. Therefore, the result of the analysis is to clarify a leading question that is a stumbling block to our students: what are the effects of social and cultural influences. The meaningful answer to this question should indicate such real effects (consequences) of social and cultural influences as:

- embeddedness in the social hierarchies existing in the given society;
- adaptability to the existing form of social organization;
- functional integration into the social organization;
- adaptability to the social communication system;
- adoption of the existing form of social management system;
- mastering the individual social roles available to a person in a certain society;
- adaptation of the individual to material and spiritual culture, which is an attribute of the vital activity of a certain society;
- mastery of verbal language and other forms of cultural communication;
- development of cultural needs and interests;
- mastering the basic material and spiritual technologies of organization of their existence, characteristic for the level of cultural development of a given society;
- mastering the skills of productive (creative) cultural activity, etc.

Social and cultural influences that have the effects of socialization and the enculturation of the individual have been refined by society for tens of millennia. Society is able to support its own systemic existence, resist the tendencies of disorganization, self-destruction only by influential social and cultural means that are components of reliable technologies of integration of the individual with the society and with the cultural environment.

Some students who, after listening to lectures revealing the essence of categorical and conceptual structures of personality as a consequence (effects) of social and cultural influences, are still ready to use this material independently in a scientific (credit or course) study. For them, a simplified version of the theoretical approach, on the basis of which a toolkit is developed to measure the effectiveness of social and cultural influences, is a competent approach. At the same time, in outlining the basic principles of the compe-

tence approach in its implication regarding the problem of measuring social and cultural effects and effectiveness, we recommend that students interpret the meaning of competence as the ability to successfully live. As a result of various social and cultural influences, a socialized and uncultured personality is formed, which, at an early stage of its development, is taught the basic skills of various activities: cognition (ability to distinguish things from one another), communication (use of non-verbal means and verbal language to designate objects and their power), actions (“activities” in the narrowest sense of the word, that is, performing expedient and purposeful actions with things). Incompetence is a delicate synonym for everyday assessments of low levels of individual development – “ignorance”, “lack of education”, “low-culture”.

Vital competence as the ability to cognitive, communicative and practical activity at the level of modern society demands is the basis for successful vital activity of the individual.

3.6. Clarification of features of use of indicators of influence of social and cultural event in development of measuring instruments of social and cultural research

The toolkit for measuring social and cultural effects and effectiveness is a set of tools for diagnosing the impact of a cultural activity on an individual or a social group. Students of the specialty “Management of social and cultural activity” are available to create a variety of questionnaires, observation programs, forms of self-reporting, self-observation, etc. to measure the client's cultural development. It is advisable for students to develop tools for measuring social and cultural effects such as:

- individual questionnaires for a particular problem. Such a questionnaire may be intended to ascertain the presence of interest, interest, acquaintance, customer orientation in a particular field of culture. It is mainly of diagnostic value. It measures the actual state of the client's education in a certain range of issues, as well as his individual attitude to various aspects of cultural life. Such diagnostic procedures are informative and useful for research orientation in the current social and cultural environment. The student acquires competencies in elementary sociological and cultural studies. Therefore, the process of developing such a tool and the results of its testing are reflected in the student's course work, and will also be useful in the first stage of conducting a graduate study of a bachelor's degree seeker;

- scales designed to measure the intensity of client perception of social and cultural phenomena and their psycho-emotional and cognitive-intellectual influence. Such measurement is a means of deepening the initial diagnostic survey. The student acquires new competencies, where the applied aspects of social-psychological theory are combined with knowledge of sociological methods;

- scales designed to measure the pragmatic aspects of a client's social and cultural life (diagnosis of behaviour associated with the objects of social

and cultural content, motivation of this behaviour, effects that occur in the pragmatic and behavioural sphere in the context of experimental changes in social and cultural).

At the first stage of students' competence to develop methods for measuring social and cultural effects and effectiveness, they are introduced to the concept of measurement in social, humanitarian and cultural studies. Differences between sociological research of public opinion and studies of social and cultural phenomena using measuring procedures are proved. At this stage, the general psycho-emotional and cognitive-intellectual nature of the process of daily measurement (evaluation) is explained by the subject of the quality of the object in accordance with his own needs, condition and composition of the environment and orientation of the changing interests. The origin of empirical-scientific measurement procedures from everyday measurement (estimation) is explained. The transition from everyday measurement (evaluation) to their abstraction of this activity into forms of counting, comparison, use of the notion of number, other graphical means of reflection of results of measurement-evaluation-comparison is clearly demonstrated.

At the same stage, it is learning the current in social studies different types of scales. In this case, there is a similar anticipation of studying a similar section in the training course "Sociology". But the program of this course, due to the limited study time, does not allow for a deliberate immersion in the procedures of social and cultural measurement of social and cultural effects and effectiveness. During practical classes and independent work of students, the development of skills in the development of simple measurement scales designed to reflect the attitude of a selected group of clients to a particular phenomenon of culture or social and cultural life.

At the next stage, students are encouraged to try and develop their own social and cultural project, which requires the development of a simple measuring tool and has practical relevance to their life and the activity of the department in which they study. The task involves the development of the project in accordance with modern rules, its design in the form of a printed document in Word format, as well as preparation of the corresponding presentation in Power Point format. It also discusses the level of information readiness of students, focuses on the features of Word tools for charting, the capabilities of Excel. Most first-year students are confident that they are sufficiently prepared to develop a mini-project using simple digital technologies. After completing homework, students' short reports are heard listening to their work progress and results. For example, in the last academic year (2018-2019) it was decided to direct the students' efforts to the development of the general theme "Preparation and conduct of the occupational orientation work at the school", subject to the individualization of its aspects. The individualization of the work was the choice of demonstration visual material

from a particular field of social and cultural activity, in which an individual student finds himself most familiar and interested.

Also, students individually selected a school in the regional centre, or in other cities of the region, to hold the event. To improve the expected results of the work, students were offered a general template for project development. The template includes such sections as the topic of the project, the name, surname and patronymic of the developer, the details of the educational institution and the department at which he studies, year of development, bibliographic description, abstract, keywords, substantiation of relevance of the project, formulation of its goals and objectives (including vocational, information, cognitive, advertising and communication tasks), project geography, target group, timeframe and duration of the event, considering the overall purpose and potential audience by budget, facilities for the study, team resources and more. The template involves explaining to the student who will be directly involved in the project implementation (what specialists are needed), for which each specialist within the project implementation plan is specifically responsible; involvement of any third parties and what specific work is envisaged by the project proposal; characterized by the author's own contribution (in the form of any services), what equipment is required to complete the project. The following is a description of the project activity process (scenario) and the project implementation timetable.

Expected results are required. It is proposed to characterize hypothetically the expected results of the event. It is necessary to write what changes the author plans to achieve as a result of the project implementation, how it will affect the target groups, other people, and society as a whole. It is required to take into account the gender composition of the future target group, to pay attention to vulnerable groups. It is suggested that quantitative and qualitative indicators be used. A requirement is the author's description of how the gender component will be taken into account in the implementation of the project activity.

Thus, it was precisely during the development of a particular project that each student developed and elaborated (mainly in a student audience during the practical classes) certain variants of measuring instruments.

Our student developed a questionnaire for high school students, designed to evaluate their familiarity with the areas in the arts that remain popular in our time, such as modernism, cubism, futurism, avant-gardism, supremacism, dadaism, hyperrealism. The study provides for measuring the growth of students' interest in these arts after a lecture given by the designer. Another student chose a topic about the role of music in a person's cultural life and a dream – the prospect of mastering the profession of music producer during a career guidance event. In her project paper, she proposes a questionnaire to measure students' interest in music culture and to increase their familiarity

with the profession of social and cultural activity manager. A questionnaire for measuring the motivation of further continuing professional education and mastering managerial specialties in college students in the specialty “carpenter-redwood” (Lebedin, Sumy region, Ukraine) was developed by a freshman who graduated from this college.

In general, as expected, the level of theoretical preparation for the development of measurement tools for measuring social and cultural effects in first-year students of the specialty “Management of social and cultural activity” was not “automatically” supported by its practical implementation. Most students developed simple questionnaires. Also, almost everyone has mastered the skill of developing nominal, ordinal, rank, interval scales, which was demonstrated during group practical classes.

4. Conclusions and discussion

On the basis of the generalization of the results of the attempt to solve the problem of forming competence to measure of social and cultural effects in students of the first year of the specialty “Management of social and cultural activity”, the following conclusions are formulated:

1. Mastering the competence to measure social and cultural effects of students of the first year of the specialty “Management of social and cultural activities” is appropriate and contributes to the deepening of the integration of theoretical and practical training of specialists, as an initial component of the system of competencies for the formation and implementation of practical social and cultural projects.

2. Educational-methodical activity on forming competence to measure of social and cultural effects occurs during the teaching of the discipline “Theory and history of social and cultural activity” in the form of 2 cycles of lectures and practical classes (forming a complex of ideas about the diversity of social and cultural activities and the concept of social and cultural activity object and subject, types, types, technologies, historical development, social and cultural process, demonstrating the concept of influence and effectiveness of social and cultural activity, mastering the goal to measure it and to make the appropriate tools.

3. Already in the first year there is a mastery of knowledge and skills to develop simple types of tools for measuring the effectiveness of some components of available social and cultural technologies. The foundations of important professional competence are laid out, which in the following courses are deepened and improved during the development of course and diploma projects.

The scientific novelty of the obtained results is a holistic understanding of measurement as a universal component of the perception of social and cultural influences by an individual and society at the everyday and scien-

tific levels; development of a system of theoretical concepts, on the basis of which the ideas of future bachelors are formed about the essence of social and cultural influences and their discretion, about the possibility of scientific measurement of social and cultural effects. The theoretical and methodological and methodological foundations of the organization of early (pre-emptive) competence formation for measuring social and cultural effects in the preparation of bachelors of the specialty "Management of social and cultural activity" are revealed. Students awareness of the essence of social and cultural influences and effects, learning the procedures of measuring the effects of social and cultural activity in the first semester of the first year helps to improve their learning in the study of the following disciplines of cultural and technological content and enables active and interested scientific and research.

The practical importance of the obtained results is manifested in the development of a practically oriented methodological approach to the teaching of the theoretical section of the discipline "History and theory of social and cultural activity", which contributes to the implementation of the principle of dual education offered at Sumy State University (Sumy, Ukraine), and to advance the competences of students.

Further research requires the improvement of certain technological components of the process of formation of professional competences in order to improve the ability to find reliable indicators used in instruments for measuring social and cultural effects.

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